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CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT PROBLEMS FACING EFL BEGINNER TEACHERS

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Abstract

This paper studies the problems that face beginner teachers during teaching EFL in secondary schools. The study investigates the classroom managements procedures that used by EFL Saudi beginner teachers. The study raises three questions. The first one is “What are the problems that face EFL beginner teachers?” the second one is “what is the level of the problems that related to Behavioral and Instructional Managements?” In addition, the third one asks, “How can we bridge between classroom language and classroom management? The study uses the historical and descriptive analytical approach. About 50 beginner secondary school teachers participate in this study. A 33-item questionnaire is distributed to 50 EFL teachers. The results show that the most problems that face beginner teachers is classroom management style’s orientation. Moreover, the results, obviously, conclude that beginner teachers did not involve into training program in advance. Therefore, the study mostly recommends that beginner teachers should be involved into intensive training courses ensuring the use of classroom management correctly and build their classroom language.

Keywords: Applied Linguistics, ELT, Classroom Management

Introduction

Wide experience in teaching EFL in all educational levels (from early school level to advance university level), will affect a lot in using classroom management. One day there was a beginner teacher teaching English lesson for third level students while a supervisor was visiting his school. The supervisor found students were silent as the teacher was explaining the lesson. The visitor did not mention even a single word. After the teacher had completed teaching process, and gave students evaluation questions about the lesson, the supervisor said that you Sudanese took seriously everything in every life situations. No one comment but later the teacher realized

that the supervisor means the way of managing the classroom. Those words wake the teacher up and put him into the right track of the classroom management. It is a controversial issue whether students' native language should be included or excluded in English language classrooms (Brown, 2000: 195), but still research findings have not been support either way. Therefore, whether agree with or not it is highly believed that bringing learners into line is a needed element for learning and teaching (Skiba & Peterson, 2003: 66). Teaching and learning is a serious task that sometimes needs an unserious process (i.e. classroom management is not only handling the lesson but also how to prepare yourself and lesson materials with all elements needed for teaching and learning settings). Consistently, Emmer, Everton & Worsham, 2003) state that classroom management embodies establishing rules to organize the class, to plan materials and activities, and to explain instructions and consequences of acting up. Concurrently, in defining classroom management, Wong & Rosemary (2001: 84) state that it is all the practices that a teacher to organize students, space, time and materials to make instruction in content and student learning can take place. Moreover, all the practices and procedures that a teacher applies to have a good classroom environment (Wong & Rosemary, 2001: 84). To achieve better classroom management teachers need to apply set of strategies to organize space, time and materials.

General Perspective

The most problems that many beginner teachers face is that they view teaching as directly transmitting information to passive learner, so that, they do not comprehend the significance of classroom management strategies and their effect on students' social academic behaviour (Torff, 2003: 563-569). Additionally, teachers need to be more careful about the strategies and techniques of managing their classes (i.e. appropriately managing classes lead to little chaos, disorder and negative behaviour in the class). It is very important to attempt training teachers in preservice and in-service education programs while there is available little teachers' behaviour in managing English classrooms.

Scholars' beliefs, concerning the nature of appropriate and inappropriate behaviours of students and how teachers manage classrooms; are vary significantly. Consequently, in a study by Martin & Yin (1997) find that females are significantly less interventionist than males regarding

instructional management and student management. In another study, Martin & Yin (1999: 101-105) find that urban teachers are significantly more interventionist than rural ones in people management whereas experienced teachers are significantly more interventionist than novice ones in relation to people and behaviour management, but not instructional management. Similarly, Chudgar & Sankar (2008: 627-642) conduct a study involve 1319 Indian teachers discover that male teachers focus more on maintaining authority in the classroom. To our best knowledge is that a novice teacher is defined as one with zero to three years teaching experience (Berliner, 1988: 39-68; Kagan, 1992: 129-169; Korevaar & Bergen,1992).

Using L1 in EFL classes

Using L1 in EFL classes is controversial in the EFL classroom. Mohammed Rhalmi (2009) reveals that monolingual approach supporters suggest that the target language should be the only medium of communication, agreeing that the lessening the use of L1 would maximize the effectiveness of learning the target language. Some teachers believe that the use of the L1 is helpful in learning new vocabulary items and explaining complex ideas and grammar rules. Moreover, they insist that teachers who master the students native language have far more advantages over the ones who don't. they claim that L1 use in EFL classes must be lowered because of many reasons.

- Use of L1 may become a habit that both learners and teachers may resort to whenever a difficulty is encountered.
- L1 may be sometimes misleading when learning the target language. In spite of the existence of universals governing language systems, languages differ more or less.
- When using L1 to teach EFL students, errors may emerge due to the L1 transfer. Examples of errors range from vocabulary to grammar. The Arab learners may also encounter difficulties related to the syntactic structures of sentences. In Arabic, the sentence structure is V-S-O while English sentences are built following the S-V-O structure. Arabic and English also differ morphologically. The morphology in Arabic is non-linear while in English it is linear.
- The use of L1 in EFL classes hinders the provision of enough comprehensible input.

The Rationale Use of L1 in EFL Learning

The problem is not using L1 communicatively inside the classroom, but when and how to use it. Concerning this issue, there has been and still there is a controversial argument between two approaches followers 'Monolingual Approach', and 'Bilingual approach'. Additionally, Deller and Rinvolutri (2002) support Nation's approach 'Balanced Approach'. They propose some examples where L1 one can be used effectively:

- **Beginners.** The mother tongue can be probably more beneficial to beginners. The time they progress in their learning the target language will take the lead.
- **L1 can be timesaving.** Instead of going through a long explanation in the target language, it is sometimes easier and more efficient to give a translation of a vocabulary item or an explanation of a grammar point.
- **Comparison.** A comparison of English and the mother tongue can be a very enriching experience. In fact, discovering the similarities and differences of both languages can enhance the TL acquisition. This comparison can be done at different levels such as vocabulary and grammar.
- **Culture.** Cultural differences and similarities can be highlighted to help learners accept and tolerate differences while at the same time preserve their cultural uniqueness. This can be done through proverbs, idiomatic expressions, songs and jokes.
- **Stress.** Using L1 gives a sense of security and acknowledges the learners identity, allowing them to minimize the stress they may feel in EFL classrooms.
- **Needs.** Beginner learners' needs must be expressed in L1 since the target language (TL) is not yet mastered. They will never be able to express and communicate their needs with a language they speak poorly.
- **Classroom management.** Management of conduct and discipline is sometimes hard to be done in the target language.

- **Grammar.** L1 can be of great help when teaching grammar. Translation exercises for example may be the perfect practice when there is a grammar point that is causing trouble to beginner students.
- **Instructions.** L1 can be used to redress learners' lack of understanding of instructions.
- **Rationale.** Students need to understand the rationale behind activities or methods. It is important that they know where they start and what they will be able to do. They should understand what lies behind the methods the teacher is using. This can only be done at this level through the students' native language.
- **Errors.** Discussion of some recurring errors. It is true that a lot of errors are caused by L1 transfer.

Actually, reasons may be applicable to other areas of EFL teaching. According to Cook (1983), one preliminary assumption is that language teaching has many goals. He adds that broad distinction can be made between external goals that relate to actual L2 use outside the classroom and internal goals that relate to the educational aims of the classroom itself.

Disciplines Concern Classroom Management

Classroom management includes, but is not limited to, discipline concerns creating an optimum instructional climate is not an easy task (Johns, et al, 1989; Lemlech, 1988; Wolfe, 1988; Wolfgang & Glickman, 1980, 1986). Relatedly, Rust (1992) reports anecdotal evidence from first-year teachers who report high levels of stress and frustration as the result of classroom management concerns. Although, more controversial assumes that, discipline was reported as a primary concern, other more general aspects of classroom management were also reported as sources of frustration. These teachers also reported a sense of shock and disillusionment with the newfound realities of the classroom. Consistently, in a longitudinal study, Niemeyer & Moon (1992) find that beginning teachers were concerned about classroom management and control.

Additionally, Kagan's (1992: 129-169) synthesis of the literature which reveals that the majority of studies indicate subjects perceive a "lack of connection" between the information provided in teacher preparation course work and the real classroom". More or less, teacher preparation

programs focused on lesson preparation and did not consider classroom management to be a fundamental concern. As there no any scholar would negate the importance of instructional planning, perhaps candidates should recently begin to recognize both effective instruction and effective classroom management as the most important and cross components of the instructional process (Johns, et al, 1989).

In early 1980s, Wolfgang and Glickman (1980, 1986), based on a combination of psychological interpretations, theorize a framework to explain teacher beliefs toward discipline. Relatedly, Wolfgang and Glickman (1980, 1986) illustrates three approaches to classroom interaction-non-interventionists, interventionists, and interactionalists. The non-interventionist presupposes the child has an inner drive that needs to find its expression in the real world. Supporters of transactional analysis or Gordon's Teacher Effectiveness Training are considered non-interventionists. On the other hand, interventionists emphasize what the outer environment (of people and objects) does to the human organism to cause it to develop in its particular way. Traditional behavior modification provides the theoretical foundation for this school of thought. Connecting between these two extremes, interactionalists focus on what the individual does to modify the external environment as well as what the environment does to shape him or her.

Beliefs regarding classroom management vary among teachers and play an important role in effective instruction. Classroom management is defined as a multi-faceted process that includes three broad dimensions -person, instruction, and discipline. Beliefs were classified on a continuum that reflects the degree of teacher power over students (Wolfgang &Glickman, 1980, 1986). The continuum is categorized into three segments; they are non-interventionist, interactionalist, and interventionist. The terms classroom management and discipline are not synonymous. The term discipline refers to the structures and rules describing the expected behavior of learners and the efforts to ensure that students comply with those rules. However, classroom management generally is defined as a broader, umbrella term that describes all teacher efforts to oversee the activities of the classroom including learning, social interaction, and student behavior.

Initially, classroom management is defined as a multi-faceted construct that includes three broad dimensions (person, instruction, and discipline). What teachers believe about students as persons and what they do to enable pupils to develop as individuals is considered a person dimension. It includes teacher's perceptions of the general nature of students' abilities as well as the overall psychosocial climate. The second dimension is the instruction dimension; it concentrates on what teachers do to enable students to learn such as the establishment and maintenance of classroom routines, physical room arrangement, and the use of time. Finally, the third one is the discipline component. It entails those behaviors that teachers use to set standards for behavior and to enforce those standards.

Wolfgang & Glickman (1980, 1986) assume that teachers believe and act according to all three models of discipline, but one usually predominates in beliefs and actions. Thus, the application of the three theories emphasizes teacher behaviors that reflect the corresponding degrees of power possessed by student and teacher.

Continually, Wolfgang & Glickman (1980: 18) define interactionist as the wary of any unilateral control of behavior by either student or teacher. Wolfgang's and Glickman's Teacher Behavior Continuum (TBC), reflects the power relationship between teacher and student techniques utilized by teachers in dealing with misbehavior: a) the child (C) enjoys the most control over his or her behavior while the teacher (T) has least control; b) oppositely, the teacher (T) assumes control of the child (C). Therefore, those who act from the non-interventionist's perspective are likely to utilize minimal power while interventionists would exercise greater control. Linking between these, interactionists strive to find joint solutions while employing some of the same techniques as non-interventionists and interventionists. Less experienced teachers differ from those with more experience regarding their attitudes pertaining to discipline. Swanson, et al (1990: 533-557) report that novice teachers tend to respond in ways that are less directive and prominent than experienced ones. Moreover, Swanson, et al (1990: 533-557) reveal that beginner teachers appeared to be patient, share responsibility, and interact with students, whereas, experienced teachers, tended to react in a manner that could be classified as more interventionist in nature (insisting on appropriate behavior, using time) out procedures, punishing students.

On the other hand, Kagan (1992: 129-169) reveals a different picture of pre-service and beginning teachers describing them as growing more controlling in their beliefs. Kagan (1992: 129-169) adds that beginner teachers began their experience by focusing on quality lesson planning. Moreover, they had begun to consider pupils as the "enemy," were overly concerned with class control, and shifted the focus of lesson planning from activities designed to encourage learning to those likely to discourage disruption (Kagan, 1992: 129-169). Kagan (1992: 129-169), therefore, states that class control and instruction appear to be inseparably interrelated pedagogical tasks. Finally, Kagan also concludes that teachers are capable of focusing on their pupils and their learning only after they have negotiated a preliminary stage in which they develop an image of themselves as teachers.

It is, therefore, hypothesized that novice teachers would score significantly more interventionist than their experienced counterparts on the Inventory of Classroom Management Style's full-scale as well as on each of the three sub-scales.

Methodology, Tools and procedure

The method used in this study to investigate the problems that face novice teachers in using classroom management is the historical and descriptive analytical approach. There are 50 participants selected randomly out of novice teachers from Qilwa General Administration of Education, i. e. 35 male and 15 female. A 33-item questionnaire contains Behavior and Instructional Management Scale adopted from Martin & Sass (2010) version. Behavior Management draws to judge how students affected from teachers' misconduct. Martin & Sass (2010) define Behavior Management as any pre-planned intervention aimed at preventing misbehavior. This includes setting rules, establishing a reward structure, and providing opportunities for student input. The second subscale is Instructional Management. Additionally, Martin & Sass (2010) reveal that Instructional Management entails teachers' styles of management within classroom life such as establishing daily procedures, allocating materials, and monitoring students' independent work. The first 12 about Behavior Management Scales and the next 12 measure the Instructional Management Scales. Concurrently, additional nine items were added to measure the extent of Arabic Language used by beginner teachers in EFL classes

and why they used that. The questionnaire was distributed to all participants. A 5-Likert point scales are used to get the views of the participants about these issues. They are ranged from strongly agree that coded (1); agree response is coded (2); not agree coded (4) and strongly disagree is coded (%) with a neutral scale that is coded (3). The duration of this research paper is done during the first semester of the academic year 2015-2016. SPSS computing program was used to calculate the results of the general view of the participants about the items targeted.

However, the questionnaire was piloted on a similar group of 15 EFL teachers to adapt them to the setting of the study and to disclose any potential problems associated. As a result, the Cronbach's α reliability coefficient was found to be 0.89. To fill out the questionnaires, the researcher obtained an oral agreement from the teachers to contribute in this study. The participants were notified that all information they provided was kept strictly confidential. Furthermore, the researcher explained to the participants that there were no right or wrong choice to the items on the questionnaire and that they should choose the most appropriate responses to the items that reflect their own points of view. Subsequently, multiple calculation and analyses were run in Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) to find out the participants' management behaviour and instruction.

Results and Analysis

Concerning the results, they were calculated according to the study questions. For more sufficient calculation and results, the variables were divided into dependent variables: they are Instructional Management and Behavioural Management. Moreover, the independent variable (teaching experience) where beginner teachers were those

Who has three or less years experience; experienced teachers were those with more than three years experience. The first question of this study is targeted the problems that face EFL beginner teachers. Hence, multiple deterioration analyses were used in order to answer the question. The following tables show the descriptive statistics for the variables.

Table 1. Variables Correlation Coefficient

Variables	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
Behavioural Management	.428	.183	-.082	.315
Instructional Management	.672	.452	-.075	.314
Teaching Experience	.816	.667	.039	.297

In the table above, the value of R (i.e. 0.428, .672 and .816) shows that the answer to the question of whether the independent variables (teaching experience) improves the predictive power of the dependent variables (Behavioural Management and Instructional Management) is accepted. So, the independent variable is considered as a predictor for the dependent variables.

Table 2. Result of ANOVA

Variables		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Behavioural Management	Regression	.824	12	.069	.191	.039
	Residual	3.676	37	.099		
	Total	4.500	49			
Instructional Management	Regression	2.032	24	.085	.158	.025
	Residual	2.468	25	.099		
	Total	4.500	49			
Teaching Experience	Regression	3.000	32	.094	1.062	.043
	Residual	1.500	17	.088		
	Total	4.500	49			

The Pearson correlations in Table 2 show that the dependent variable of behavioral management and instructional management correlate with the independent variable. The significance values for the independent variables (teaching experience) were less than 0.05. Therefore, the independent variables could improve the accuracy of the prediction of behavioral management and instructional management. Consequently, the second null hypothesis is not accepted. The second research question sought to explore the relationship between participants' teaching experience and their instructional and behavioural management. Various regression analyses were used in order to answer the second research question. The interesting point is that there was a significant negative correlation between the dependent variables (behavioral management and instructional management) ($p = 0.039$ and 0.25) and teaching experience ($p = 0.047$) for all the results (i.e. as the teaching experience of the participants increased their instructional and behavioural managements style become more negative). Therefore, the independent variables

(teaching experience) could improve the accuracy of the prediction of instructional management and behavioural management. Concurrently, the third hypothesis that aimed at bridging between classroom language and classroom management, is accepted too (i.e. as the experience of the teacher increased the use of the target language in managing the class is increased and that facilitates the classroom management).

Discussion, Summary and Conclusions

The results above indicate that beginner teachers scored significantly more interventionist in their perceptions of classroom management style than experienced teachers ($F_{4,500} = 191$; $p < .05$). In addition, beginner teachers and experienced teachers differed significantly in both Instructions ($F_{.158} = .025$; $p < .05$) and ($F_{1.062} = .043$; $p < .05$). No significant difference was determined regarding the Person dimension. These results reflect that the wrong perceptions of beginner teachers towards classroom management may be influenced by their little experience of teaching rather than their own views. Those little experienced teachers may have improve their beliefs and practices to link to particular teaching realities and which exploit on classroom-based problem solving skills learned on the job later.

In the eyes of teachers' views, classroom management is considered one of the most warning and widespread problems in education (Johns et al, 1989). Beliefs regarding the nature of appropriate and inappropriate student behaviors; and how to manage classrooms vary among teachers and can play an important role in the determination of teachers' behavior (Willower et al, 1967: 5-8; Wolfgang & Glickman, 1986). The current study investigated the relationship between teaching experience and behavior and instructional classroom management approaches adopted by EFL teachers in Saudi Arabia. The findings reflect that the dependent variable, teaching experience, predicted the improvement of teachers' behavioral and instructional management orientations. The finding of this research is in line with the conclusions revealed by Chudgar and Sankar. Chudgar & Sankar (2008) discovered that teachers focused more on maintaining authority in the classroom. Similarly, Unal and Unal (2012) found a significant relationship between behavior management and instructional management in the years of teaching experience. This, then, seems an area fruitful for future research.

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Appendix

Questionnaire

Dear colleague,

Please, show your point of view accordingly about these items. They are about the problems that face EFL beginner teachers. Your idea is highly needed and is going to be used only for the purpose of academic research. This questionnaire consists of **two sections**. **Section one**, asks about your experience and qualification degree whereas **section two** concentrates on classroom management items.

Section 1. Tick () that best describes your qualification and experience.

Qualification	Bachelor degree	(<input type="checkbox"/>)	Diploma	(<input type="checkbox"/>)	Other (mention it)
Experience	Three years or less	(<input type="checkbox"/>)	More than three years	(<input type="checkbox"/>)	

Section 2. Write the number that best describes your opinion about the following items.

Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Not agree	Strongly not agree
1	2	3	4	5

1. I always intervene when students talk at inappropriate times during class.	
2. I limit student chatter in the classroom.	
3. I reward students for good behavior in the classroom.	
4. If a student talks to a neighbor, I will move the student away from other students.	
5. I use input from students to create classroom rules.	
6. I allow students to get out of their seat without permission.	
7. I am strict when it comes to student compliance in my classroom.	
8. I firmly redirect students back to the topic when they get off task.	
9. I insist that students in my classroom follow the rules at all times.	
10. I closely monitor off task behavior during class.	
11. I strictly enforce classroom rules to control student behavior.	
12. I demand defiant student's behavior to comply my classroom rules.	
13. I use whole class instruction to ensure a controlled classroom.	

14. I always use collaborative learning to explore questions in the classroom.	
15. I engage students in active discussion about issues related to real world issues.	
16. I establish a teaching daily routine in my classroom and stick to it.	
17. I always use group work in my classroom.	
18. I use student input when creating student projects.	
19. I always use inquiry-based learning in the classroom.	
20. I direct the students' transition from one learning activity to another.	
21. I always adjust instruction in response to individual student needs.	
22. I nearly always use direct instruction when I teach.	
23. I do not deviate from my pre-planned learning activities.	
24. I always use a teaching approach that encourages interaction among students.	
25. I have graduated in a faculty of education.	
26. I have taken a training session before starting my job as an EFL teacher.	
27. I consider classroom management to be a fundamental concern that push learning forward.	
28. I use only Arabic in teaching EFL.	
29. I use Arabic in teaching EFL because my students understand better.	
30. I use Arabic in teaching EFL because it is easy for me to teach.	
31. I use Arabic because it helps me control my students better.	
32. I use Arabic in EFL classes because it motivates students' learning.	
33. I use Arabic in EFL classes because it shows my power that I control the class better.	